

A Simulation Approach for the Impact Assessment of an Axial Flux Traction Motor Applied on Road Electric Vehicle

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Abstract

In the transition towards sustainable mobility, Circular Design principles are crucial. Electric Motors are subject to continuous innovation to improve efficiency, performance density and reduce externalities associated with their production. Therefore, the choice of technological solutions during design phase must guarantee optimal performance and minimal environmental impact throughout the entire product life cycle: production, use, and end-of-life. In the automotive sector, the use phase is particularly critical since the efficiency of the traction system is directly related to total energy consumption during the life cycle and, consequently, to its environmental impact. This research introduces a simulation-based approach to evaluate the use phase of an Axial Flux Electric Motor equipped with Permanent Magnets (AFPM). While providing high performance for electric traction motors, these magnets are composed of Rare Earth Elements (REEs), e.g. Neodymium, classified as Critical Raw Materials (CRMs) due to limited availability and environmental

concerns associated with extraction and processing. However, the high torque and power density of this motor technology can potentially reduce the use of CRMs compared to other design solutions. The primary objective of this study is to show a preliminary scalable model that allows designers to evaluate motor performance under different design choices and use scenarios, defined through standard or custom driving cycles, providing immediate feedback in terms of environmental impact. The latter is evaluated by analyzing the powertrain's energy consumption and efficiency using a road vehicle model, compiling the use phase inventory quickly, and simplifying access to information. This preliminary model thus serves as a decision-support system to balance performance optimization and environmental sustainability during the design phase. This work is part of a framework aimed at improving circularity of industrial products, particularly in the automotive industry. Incorporating environmental factors in design phases encourages innovative solutions that enhance efficiency and decrease reliance on limited resources.

Introduction

In the context of the global shift toward environmental sustainability as a key measure to combat climate change, the automotive industry is undergoing a significant transformation to promote more sustainable forms of mobility. In detail, the growing adoption of Electric Vehicles (EVs), including Battery Electric Vehicles (BEVs) and hydrogen Fuel Cell Electric Vehicles (FCEVs), is mainly driven by several international climate agreements. In Europe, for example, the European Green Deal [1] strongly supports industrial production that progressively aligns with environmental, economic, and social sustainability criteria. Given this accelerated growth in electric vehicle technology, it is evident that the demand for traction Electric Motors (EMs) in the automotive sector [2] will increase as a consequence. In this scenario, axial flux

electric motors represent a promising technological solution [3]. This innovative configuration enables significantly higher energy density and more compact design solutions than conventional radial motors [3]. Various electric motors designed for automotive traction commonly incorporate Permanent Magnets (PMs) [4], which enable them to achieve remarkable power densities and efficiencies; not surprisingly, AFPM units have been frequently proposed for the adoption on powered two-wheelers [5]. However, the permanent magnets used in these motors often use Rare Earth Elements (REEs) [6] such as Neodymium, Dysprosium, and Praseodymium, which are listed among the Critical Raw Materials (CRMs) [7] due to their significant environmental and social impact [8, 9, 10, 11]. In addition, copper, which is widely used in motor stator windings, is classified as a Strategic Raw

Material (SRM) [7], highlighting its critical importance and strategic relevance. Adopting a Circular Design approach is becoming increasingly important as part of the ongoing shift toward a Circular Economy model [12, 13, 14]. Embracing the principles of Circular Design involves carefully considering the potential circularity of the product throughout the entire life cycle from the earliest stages of design [15]. The importance and encouragement to integrate these design paradigms into product development processes can be derived from the Critical Raw Materials Act (CRMA) [16]. Thus, research into reducing the use of these materials and simultaneously improving their circularity becomes relevant [17, 18, 19]. Such recommendations directly involve, for example, End-of-Life (EoL) stage considerations [20], emphasizing product design solutions that facilitate easy disassembly and recycling of materials. To accurately quantify the environmental impacts of industrial products, the methodological framework of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), standardized by ISO 14040:2006 [21], could be applied. When assessing the life cycle impacts of a product, it is essential to consider all relevant stages, from initial production through the use phase and to end-of-life management. In the automotive sector, in particular, the use phase can contribute significantly to the total life cycle impact [22] of in-vehicle products, mainly because of an average vehicle's long life, i.e., high mileage. It is therefore critical, from the earliest design stages [23], to thoroughly evaluate how certain design choices affect not only the manufacturing phase, but also other phases of the life cycle, including use and disposal. For electric motors, certain design choices that seem intuitively aligned with sustainable manufacturing, such as the assembly of permanent magnets without bonding or the use of recycled materials, could affect the motor's efficiency under different operating conditions, consequently affecting energy consumption. The motor's energy consumption is directly related to the environmental impact associated with the electricity production required for its operation [24, 25, 26]. The intensity of this impact depends also on the industrial energy mix specific to the geographic region where electricity is generated and/or consumed [27]. In the broader perspective of developing a comprehensive framework aimed at systematically and holistically assessing the impacts of automotive components, particularly in the specific case study of Axial Flux Permanent Magnets (AFPM) electric motors, it becomes essential not only to calculate manufacturing impacts but also to rigorously examine how design choices affect operational performance and end-of-life management. Particular attention must be given, for example, to the ease of disassembly of components and their recyclability [28, 29]. Instead, the study presented in this paper focuses on the use phase of the case study, introducing a preliminary simulation model designed to integrate into a broader, more general framework of impact analysis that also considers the life cycle phases of production and end-of-life. This model aims to support engineers and decision-makers in identifying and selecting optimal design strategies for AFPM electric motors by assessing the potential implications each design

alternative could have during the product's use phase. Therefore, this study uses the Global Warming Potential (GWP 100, expressed in kg CO_{2-eq}) as the main environmental impact reference for system assessment. This simulation approach aims to facilitate innovative and sustainable design solutions in the automotive industry.

Methods

The objective of this study is to develop a simulation-based framework for the preliminary assessment of the use-phase impact of an AFPM electric motor. The methodology focuses on vehicle behavior across various driving cycles. The framework requires several user-defined inputs. Specifically, motor modeling relies on an efficiency map defined as a function of torque and rotational speed. Additionally, vehicle modeling necessitates input data to characterize longitudinal dynamics. The driver control system also requires target speed profiles to regulate vehicle motion. These profiles are derived from standard or custom driving cycles assigned to the simulated vehicle. By simulating traction and regenerative braking via the electric motor, the system computes energy consumption over the driving cycle, normalized per kilometer. This average energy consumption is then used to estimate the environmental impact. The impact is calculated based on the energy production mix of the geographical regions under consideration, where the vehicle is assumed to be charged and operated. These data, available from specific environmental databases, enable the calculation of several impact indicators across relevant categories. The framework thus enables a rapid pre-assessment of both the environmental impact and performance of the motor, supporting users in efficiently evaluating design variations, across different geographic contexts, vehicle types, and standard or customized driving cycles. The framework is developed in Matlab/Simulink environment (MATLAB version R2024b) [30]. It is important to note that the approach has been designed to be scalable and adaptable to a wide range of vehicle categories, from light quadricycles to motorcycles and high-performance cars. As a result, it can be adapted to motors of different sizes and performance requirements, providing a flexible and robust tool for preliminary design choices in different automotive applications. A schematic summary of the proposed methodology, which is detailed in the following sections, is presented in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1 Framework methodology workflow.

AFPM Motor Efficiency Map

As part of this study, which focuses on modeling and simulating the use phase of an Axial Flux Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor (AFPMSM), a vehicle model capable of accurately estimating energy consumption of several driving cycles was used. The primary input this vehicle model requires, in terms of motor characteristics, is an efficiency map expressed as a function of torque and rotational speed. Consequently, developing a realistic efficiency map suitable for integration into the simulation is essential. An analytical modeling approach was adopted to achieve this goal, which allows simplified but efficient and fast estimation of various electrical losses under different operating conditions. This modeling approach permits parameterizing various physical and operational characteristics of the AFPM motor, such as the number of poles, maximum torque, maximum speed, and other characteristics dependent on its design and topology. Parameterization allows for rapid calculation of efficiency maps that closely approximate actual conditions. However, they could be less accurate than dedicated simulations using Finite Element Methods (FEM) or Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), given the intrinsic three-dimensional nature of this type of motor [31, 32]. At each operating point, efficiency is calculated as the ratio of the required mechanical output power to the electrical input power required to generate that mechanical power. The electrical input power includes the required mechanical power and the losses resulting from the conversion process between electrical and mechanical form. In accordance with methods arising from literature [33, 34, 35, 36] total losses were approximated as the sum of several loss components, as shown in Equation 1.

$$P_{\text{losses}} = P_{\text{cu}} + P_{\text{fe}} + P_{\text{mag}} + P_{\text{mech}} \quad (1)$$

In Equation 1, P_{cu} represents copper losses, P_{fe} represents iron losses, P_{mag} represents magnetic losses, and P_{mech} represents mechanical losses. Copper losses [37, 38, 39] are calculated based on Equation 2, simplifying methods used in literature.

$$P_{\text{cu}} = 3 \cdot I^2 \cdot R_s \cdot k_{\text{cu}} \quad (2)$$

I is the current calculated considering torque, stator resistance, number of poles and flux linkage. The stator resistance R_s is determined by Equation 3, which incorporates a correction related to the motor operating temperature T_{op} [40], α_{cu} is the temperature coefficient of resistance for copper. The correction factor k_{cu} approximates skin and proximity effects [37, 38, 41, 42] and is calculated by Equation 4. The frequency f is determined by the number of poles and the rotation speed, while a , b , m and n are empirical correction factors.

$$R_s = R_{s,\text{ref}} \cdot \left[1 + \alpha_{\text{cu}} \cdot (T_{\text{op}} - 20) \right] \quad (3)$$

$$k_{\text{cu}} = 1 + a \cdot f^m + b \cdot f^n \quad (4)$$

Iron losses are calculated using Bertotti's model [43, 44] as shown in Equation 5, which explicitly considers the

effects of hysteresis, eddy currents, and excess losses, characterized by empirical coefficients assumed to be constant: k_h , k_e , and k_{ex} , respectively. Term B represents the peak flux density, m_{fe} the mass of iron.

$$P_{\text{fe}} = m_{\text{fe}} \cdot \left[\left(k_h \cdot f \cdot B^2 \right) + \left(k_e \cdot f^2 \cdot B^2 \right) + \left(k_{\text{ex}} \cdot f^{1.5} \cdot B^{1.5} \right) \right] \quad (5)$$

Magnetic losses [45, 46] are estimated simply by multiplying an empirical coefficient k_{mag} by the square of the frequency, as indicated by Equation 6.

$$P_{\text{mag}} = k_{\text{mag}} \cdot f^2 \quad (6)$$

Finally, mechanical losses [47, 48, 49] are calculated according to Equation 7, comprising a constant torque component multiplied by the rotational speed ω , plus an additional component proportional to the cube of the rotational speed through the coefficient k_{wind} .

$$P_{\text{mech}} = T_{0,\text{friction}} \cdot \omega + k_{\text{wind}} \cdot \omega^3 \quad (7)$$

This modeling methodology produces rapidly a sufficiently realistic efficiency map for preliminary evaluations and simulation studies of electric vehicle consumption. In addition, it allows quick modification of parameters related directly to AFPM motor design, facilitating iterative optimization. Among the parameters that can be adjusted during map generation are key performance characteristics such as maximum torque and rotational speed, allowing the model to represent motors with varying power levels, from small, compact, low-power units to high-performance machines. This flexibility makes the approach inherently scalable and adaptable to a wide range of automotive applications. The efficiency map used in the study is shown in Figure 2, and it was generated through the use of consistent values, based on real case studies, market benchmark, and author's experience, for the study of the use phase of an Axial Flux Permanent Magnet electric motor. The case study here considered adopts a range of torque and RPM which is comparable,

FIGURE 2 AFPM electric motor efficiency map.

for example, to the level needed for high-performance sport motorcycles [50].

Road Electric Vehicle Model

The vehicle simulation model adopted in the present study is an updated and adapted version of the car model previously introduced by Berzi et al. [51, 52]. Specifically designed to estimate the energy consumption of electric and hybrid vehicles, the model incorporates several simplifications to facilitate quick simulations over various driving cycles. The longitudinal dynamic is considered sufficient since the main objective is to estimate vehicle energy consumption accurately and efficiently. The analysis does not include lateral dynamics, load transfer phenomena, and the distinction between sprung and unsprung masses, because they were considered negligible for this type of study. The developed model considers essential parameters such as vehicle mass, aerodynamic drag, tire rolling resistance, and a comprehensive representation of the various efficiency losses in the driveline components. These losses include, among others, the mechanical inefficiencies that occur in the drivetrain system. The following sections detail the main elements constituting the model, which was implemented in the Matlab/Simulink environment. Figure 3 shows a schematic diagram of the entire simulation model.

Battery Model The vehicle battery pack is represented through an equivalent circuit system model characterized by an arrangement of voltage sources, resistors, and capacitors. This modeling approach simplifies the calculation of the battery State of Charge (SOC) and temperature-related performance effects during operation. In addition, the battery model includes an optional aging function, which allows the simulation of battery performance degradation over extended periods.

Electric Motor and Powertrain Model As previously introduced, the *Electric Motor* subsystem receives efficiency maps as input, defined as a function of torque and rotational speed. The EM model includes Powertrain elements typical of front-axle traction vehicles, such as a

reduction and differential unit and an integrated inverter. The model can potentially include Range Extender (REX), and Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicles (PHEVs) solutions, which are not used in this application which is focused on pure EVs.

Driver Model The driver system is represented by a Proportional-Integral (PI) control algorithm. It receives a target speed based on the chosen driving cycle as input, calculates the error between this target speed and the effective vehicle speed, and then produces output signals corresponding to acceleration or braking requirements. The braking commands are divided into two distinct components: regenerative braking, and mechanical braking torque according to a suitable brake blending strategy, in this case with a series architecture. Motor-generated and mechanically generated torque signals directly influence the vehicle speed dynamics, represented by the *Car Body* subsystem, through the resulting longitudinal forces.

Power Control Unit and Auxiliary Systems Energy demands associated with the vehicle's auxiliary systems, such as the air conditioning system, are modeled based on statistical distributions derived from empirical field experiments. Energy consumption data from the electric motor and auxiliary systems are the input to the *Power Control Unit* model.

Driving Cycles

After describing the simulation model used, in which the driver operates the vehicle according to the target speeds predicted by the selected driving cycles, it is necessary to outline which driving cycles were adopted and the rationale behind their selection. In automotive applications, driving cycles are widely used for type-approval purposes, mainly to evaluate vehicles' fuel consumption and emissions before they are placed on the market. These cycles specify the exact durations in which vehicles must adhere to particular speed profiles divided into segments, or phases, of testing, thus replicating vehicle operations as realistically as possible.

The first cycle used in this study is the Worldwide Harmonized Light Vehicles Test Cycle (WLTC) [53], defined by the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE), an evolution of the previous New European Driving Cycle (NEDC). Specifically, the version applied in the study is Class 3b, designed for vehicles capable of exceeding 120 km/h. This cycle lasts 30 minutes, traveling about 23.3 km reaching a maximum speed of 131.3 km/h. The cycle is divided into four segments: three represent low, medium, and high-speed conditions, plus an extra-high speed segment. The WLTC is one of the most realistic driving cycles currently available and includes several versions depending on the vehicle's power-to-mass ratio (PMR).

The second cycle adopted in this work is the FTP-75 (Federal Test Procedure) cycle [54, 55] developed by the

FIGURE 3 Road Electric Vehicle Model layout.

U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), which aims to emulate cold and hot start conditions. This cycle covers a distance of 17.8 km with a maximum speed of 91.2 km/h. It includes three segments: an initial cold start phase, a transient driving phase with varying speeds, and finally, a phase that simulates a hot start. Between the second and third phases there is a 10 minute “hot soak” rest phase. Notably, this cycle has a significant duration at engine idle conditions.

The third driving cycle is the Japanese JC08 cycle [55], designed to represent Japan’s particularly congested urban driving conditions. This cycle lasts about 20 minutes and covers a distance of 8.2 km, with a maximum speed of 81.6 km/h. It includes both the cold start and driving warm-up phase.

Finally, the study uses one of the driving cycles developed by Berzi et al. [56] as part of the ASTERICS project [57]. This cycle integrates empirical data collected through road tests in the city of Florence, Italy. Specifically, cycle “ASTERICS all long” was chosen, characterized by a duration of about 25 minutes, driving about 11.6 km, with an average speed of about 27.1 km/h and a maximum speed of 85.7 km/h. The driving cycles of Berzi et al. [56] were originally designed to simulate electric vehicles, making them particularly suitable for comparative analyses with other cycles. The graph of the driving cycles used in this work is shown in Figure 4.

In conclusion, the selected driving cycles used in this research facilitate the creation of a driver command sequence within the vehicle simulation model, dictating the traction and braking torque demands from the electric motor (and mechanical brakes). Ultimately, this approach quantifies energy consumption during each cycle and,

ideally, throughout the entire use phase of the vehicle life cycle.

Comparisons between Driving Cycles Some analyses were conducted to compare the dynamic characteristics of the driving cycles used in the simulations. To compare the characteristics of the cycles, two graphs are presented using significant descriptors, such as the relationship between positive and negative accelerations and speed-acceleration correlations. These indicators are intrinsic to the cycle itself and do not depend on the specific model or case study. The aim is to show how the reference cycles adopted modify the performance required of the vehicle; this variability motivates the need to test the vehicle’s performance on the basis of different cycles, in order to ensure that any optimization action is not punctual but verified on different missions, thus resulting in a probable global optimization.

The first analysis compares the average positive and negative accelerations for each cycle. The accelerations were calculated as finite differences between consecutive speed samples, as shown in Equation 8, using a time step of 1 second.

$$a_i = \frac{V_{i+1} - V_i}{dt} \quad (8)$$

For each cycle, the average of the positive accelerations and the average absolute value of the negative accelerations were calculated. The results are illustrated in Figure 5, which shows the differences in the averages of acceleration and deceleration between cycles.

The second analysis, shown in Figure 6, presents a two-dimensional acceleration distribution as a function of instantaneous speed. The data are separated into acceleration and deceleration phases, and the relative density of the points is evaluated using Kernel Density

FIGURE 4 Driving cycles time-speed data.

FIGURE 5 Average positive and negative accelerations of driving cycles.

FIGURE 6 Acceleration distribution as a function of speed.

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Estimation (KDE) [58]. KDE is a non-parametric technique for estimating the probability density function of a variable and, in this context, highlights regions in the speed-acceleration space where data points are more concentrated. The estimated densities are mapped to color intensity, with red indicating higher densities and blue the lower ones. This visualization enables a clear understanding of the range of values covered and the relative frequency of each speed-acceleration combination throughout the cycle. Compared to discrete representations such as scatter plots or histograms, this approach provides a smoother and more continuous visualization of the underlying data distribution. As in the previous case, all cycles were uniformly sampled at 1 Hz. The graphs show the accelerations most reported within the various cycles, especially the ASTERICS cycle deviates from the homologative cycles with the presence of some points with higher acceleration and deceleration.

Electricity Production

Once the vehicle's energy consumption during the driving cycle has been calculated, it becomes critical to determine the environmental, social, and economic impacts associated with this energy use. Within the scope of this study, particular emphasis is placed on the environmental impacts resulting from the production of electricity consumed during the use phase of the electric motor, which is intrinsically linked to the motor's design and manufacturing processes. In fact, during the operating phase of the motor, the primary source of environmental impact is the electrical energy consumed, which increases as the motor power losses increase, that is, as its efficiency decreases. However, it is important to note that changes in efficiency do not necessarily lead to significant changes in the overall calculated impact. For example, a motor with slightly lower peak efficiency but an optimized efficiency distribution in the most common operating

zones of driving cycles could significantly reduce overall energy consumption. Although electric vehicles are often described as having "zero emissions" at the time of use, their environmental impact depends strongly on the electricity generation processes they consume. Electricity generation is characterized by specific energy mixes, representing different proportions of generation from various energy sources and technologies. For example, electricity can come from renewable energy sources, such as wind or solar power, or from more environmentally damaging sources, such as coal-fired generation. Therefore, the weighted average environmental footprint associated with electricity generation can be expressed as the equivalent impact per kilowatt-hour (kWh). Four geographic locations were selected in this analysis: Europe (RER), United States (US), Japan (JP), and Italy (IT). This geographic diversity allows us to compare the environmental impacts from different national (or continental) electricity generation mixes and analyze the driving cycles and consumption patterns specific to each region. The data used in this study came from the Ecoinvent v3.10.1 database [59]. The Environmental Footprint (EF) v3.1 Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) methodology were used, as recommended by European Union Commission [60]. Specifically, datasets corresponding to market activities for each of the examined geographical regions were selected and analyzed. Environmental impact analyses were conducted on impact categories related to climate change, use of non-renewable energy resources, and acidification. The three respective indicators used are Global Warming Potential (GWP 100) expressed in kg CO_{2-eq}; Abiotic Depletion Potential (ADP) related to fossil fuels, expressed in MJ; and Accumulated Exceedance (AE), expressed in mol H⁺_{eq}.

Results

Two analyses were conducted using a simulation-based approach to evaluate the use phase of electric motors. The first is focused on quantifying energy consumption over several standardized driving cycles, considering country-specific electric generation mixes. The second examined the implications of changing motor characteristics, particularly the efficiency map, to assess how alternative design choices might affect environmental performance.

Driving Cycle-Based Energy Consumption and Impact Assessment

The initial simulation was configured using the efficiency map shown in Figure 1, with realistic constraints applied to the maximum torque levels during the traction and regenerative braking phases. The simulated vehicle is a C-segment sedan, for which realistic and relevant parameters such as component masses, dynamic properties, and

aerodynamic coefficients were defined. Energy consumption was calculated for each driving cycle. The results include total electrical energy used per kilometer and net energy consumption, considering energy recovered through regenerative braking; they are summarized in Table 1.

The “Net” energy assessment may vary significantly for a same vehicle class depending on manufacturer implementation, powertrain characteristics, and regenerative braking settings which can depend on selected driving mode; the proposed calculation is based on the hypothesis of a quite accurate brake blending capability of the vehicle. Figure 7 presents a comparison between the reference speed profiles and the battery power, both requested during traction and stored during regenerative phases, across the analyzed driving cycles. This analysis offers a clearer understanding of the vehicle’s energy interaction with the battery, allowing for a more precise estimation of the net energy consumption over the course of the driving cycle.

Two separate analyses were performed using the simulation results. The first analysis applied the life

cycle impact indicators to the energy consumption observed during the WLTC - Class 3b driving cycle, combined with the energy generation profiles of the various geographic zones. The results of this country-specific impact assessment are shown in Figure 8. The graphs show how the environmental impact of an electric vehicle undergoing a specific driving cycle depends strongly on how the energy mix is produced in that specific geographical area.

The second analysis aims to match each country’s characteristic driving cycle with its respective electricity generation mix. Specifically, for Europe, the WLTC - Class 3b was used; for the United States, the FTP-75; and for Japan, the JC08. The “ASTERICS - all long” cycle was chosen for Italy because it was derived from real driving data in Italian urban settings, particularly in Florence. The environmental impacts calculated from this country-cycle alignment are presented in Figure 9.

As explained in detail in the “Discussion” paragraph, the results shown in Figure 9 are due both to technical reasons related to the vehicles (different time-speed cycles in different market areas) and to reasons related to the geographical context (impact of electricity production, different for each area).

TABLE 1 Energy Consumed by Driving Cycles, total and net.

Energy Used by Driving Cycle	Total [Wh/km]	Net [Wh/km]
WLTC – Class 3b	207	164
FTP-75	186	130
JC08	175	119
ASTERICS – all long	226	124

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FIGURE 7 In red the power required and stored in the battery during driving cycles. In blue the reference speed of the selected driving cycle.

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Design Comparison and Impact Assessment via Simulation

The second part of the study demonstrates how this simulation approach can be leveraged to evaluate the circularity and sustainability of different motor design strategies beyond simple performance parameters. Specifically, the analysis compares two design scenarios: a baseline configuration and a modified one

FIGURE 8 Environmental impacts by country using WLTC driving cycle.

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FIGURE 9 Global Warming Potential by country using different driving cycles.

representing a design with reduced impacts in the production phase but higher energy consumption. Due to the absence of primary data for the production and EoL phases of the motor, the baseline scenario is based on secondary data present in Ecoinvent for a generic electric vehicle motor production. The comparative analysis involves the calculation of the Break Even Point (BEP), defined as the mileage at which the cumulative environmental benefit of a more efficient motor offsets its more significant manufacturing impact or vice versa. In the modified scenario, the motor design is assumed to result in a 20% reduction in carbon footprint at production (expressed in CO₂-eq). However, this gain comes at the cost of a reduced operational efficiency, resulting in an increase of 5% in energy consumption per kilometer during the use phase. This scenario models a hypothetical design strategy focused on circularity and material sustainability, prioritizing emissions reduction during production even if this results in higher energy consumption during use. In this context, the BEP indicates the distance the vehicle must travel before operational inefficiency outweighs the production advantage. A low BEP means that the increase in energy consumption during use quickly negates the initial advantage, suggesting that the design may not be environmentally beneficial over the typical lifespan of a vehicle. On the contrary, a high BEP implies that the production advantage remains dominant over a long operating range, making the design more favorable from a lifecycle perspective. The BEP analysis was conducted using the WLTC driving cycle and considering the average European electric generation mix. Environmental impacts per km were calculated for both cases using energy consumption during the driving cycle and then aggregated over increasing travel distances.

The results presented in Figure 10 reveal the cross-over point where the more significant impact of the use phase of the less efficient design outweighs the benefit of the reduced emissions of the production phase. This result underscores how trade-offs between performance and life-cycle impacts must be considered holistically in sustainable design decisions.

FIGURE 10 Break Even Point Analysis for two different motor design.

Discussion and Future Developments

Analysis of the simulation results presented in the previous section reveals several significant aspects. First, there is a marked difference in energy consumption among the different driving cycles. In particular, the WLTC - Class 3b cycle has significantly higher net energy consumption (Wh/km) than the other three cycles. In contrast, the ASTERICS - all long cycle stands out for its extensive use of regenerative braking. Despite initially appearing to be the most energy-intensive of the four, it achieves the second lowest net energy consumption, highlighting the central role of regeneration strategies in reducing overall energy demand. When evaluating the impact of the electric motor use phase in different countries using the same driving cycle (WLTC), it is evident that each geographic region has advantages and disadvantages based on specific environmental impact categories. For example, the graphs in Figure 8 show that the impact in Japan is significant, not necessarily due to the driving cycle employed, but rather because of the strong reliance on fossil fuels in the energy mix production. This variation underscores the absence of a universally optimal region for electricity generation from an environmental perspective. Regarding climate change, measured in CO₂ equivalent emissions, European countries have a more sustainable energy mix with relatively lower emissions. However, the secondary data used are static and the generation of current is not only geographically dependent but also time variant for the use of renewable energies.

The second part of the analysis, which matches each country's driving cycle to its type-approval test, provides further insight. Although aligning driving cycles with regional contexts introduces small shifts in the rankings, the overall trend in global warming potential (GWP100)

remains relatively constant (Figure 9). The most striking deviation is the improvement in Italy's performance relative to the European average when using the "ASTERICS - all long" cycle, reiterating the benefits of regenerative braking in improving energy recovery and reducing net consumption.

The final analysis represents the core contribution of this study. It investigates how design choices oriented towards circularity, particularly in reducing the motor manufacturing phase's environmental burden, affect the electric motor's total life cycle impact. It is well-known that, in automotive components, the use phase typically dominates the life cycle impacts. For passive components, weight reduction is a common sustainability strategy. While it may increase production impacts, it can decrease fuel or energy consumption during use, with a calculable break-even point in kilometers driven. This is usually indicated by the change in Fuel Consumption (FC) relative to mass, thus finding the Fuel Reduction Value (FRV) [61]. However, for active components such as the electric motor, where energy consumption is intrinsic to the use phase, the trade-off shifts. Electric motors, especially those with high efficiency across a wide torque-speed range, already use the available energy well. Still, production impacts remain an issue, particularly when permanent magnets with REEs are involved. Efforts to reduce these impacts through improved material choices or circular design strategies (e.g., mechanical assembly over adhesives or resins) must ensure minimal efficiency loss over the vehicle's lifetime. The analysis found that even with a 20% reduction in production-related impact, an optimistic yet exemplary scenario, and a relatively modest 5% increase in energy consumption per kilometer, the break-even point is reached before the expected vehicle lifespan (Figure 10). This finding underscores the importance of a holistic, early-stage assessment of various motor designs. Developing a tool to evaluate the performance and environmental impacts of various design alternatives could provide valuable suggestions to designers. Such a system, based on accessible data like the Bill of Materials (BOM) or motor efficiency maps, would improve decision-making even for non-experts in LCA or motor design.

Analytical and database-derived inputs are used to develop the results of this study, with a simulative approach that is useful even in early design stages when products' primary data is not defined. At the current stage of implementation, the calculation framework can provide a scenario comparison, as shown in this document, aggregating data from the user, from the traction electric powertrain numerical data and from different scenario in a single calculation environment; also, the analysis, after input definition, requires a processing time of only a few minutes on a desktop machine. The simulation-based approach to evaluating performance and sustainability during the motor's use phase is intended to be part of a broader framework. This future framework will include assessments of impacts during the production phase. It will also incorporate EoL considerations, including environmental credits associated with the functional recycling

of critical and strategical materials found in AFPM motors, such as rare earth elements in magnets and copper in stator windings. Furthermore, the use-phase model developed here can be flexibly applied, whether using analytically derived efficiency maps, experimentally measured maps (e.g. with bench testing), or those generated via advanced software analysis such as FEM and CFD. The analytical approach enables rapid comparisons of different motor designs, especially when combined with scaling laws specific to axial flux machines [62], which facilitate the recalculation of losses and performance characteristics based on geometric variations.

Conclusion

The study presents a simulation-based approach to analyze the use phase performance of an Axial Flux Permanent Magnet (AFPM) electric motor. This approach is part of the definition of a pre-assessment framework in the design phase that integrates the principles of circular design. In particular, the simulation model was constructed using analytical or semi-empirical laws to construct an efficiency map, which allows for adjustment of the motor's characteristics according to various design parameters, enabling the model to represent motors with variable power levels, from small powertrains to high-performance machines. This motor model has been integrated with a more general vehicle model, thus allowing variations between different vehicle categories, from light quadricycles to powerful cars. In particular, a C-segment vehicle was analyzed. Consequently, different scenarios can be analyzed to assess whether changes in the electric motor's performance can meet the needs of various vehicles subjected to different driving cycles. The model obtained provides information on the energy consumption of the electric motor during the use phase, which, depending on the energy mix used to generate electricity, can be used to calculate the associated environmental impacts, subdivided according to the geographical region analyzed. In addition, the model lends itself to analyzing the different design variants using Break Even Point (BEP) to verify how many kilometers a solution is more sustainable than another. This preliminary methodological approach thus lays the basis for a more detailed analysis of the use phase, allowing an assessment of how product design changes, made according to eco-friendly design principles, influence environmental performance at different life cycle stages. Finally, this approach will be a valuable decision-making tool for the various stakeholders in the automotive industry.

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Definitions/Abbreviations

AFPM - Axial Flux Permanent Magnets electric motor

REE - Rare Earth Element

CRM - Critical Raw Material

EV - Electric Vehicle

BEV - Battery Electric Vehicle

FCEV - Fuel Cell Electric Vehicle

EM - Electric Motor

PM - Permanent Magnet

SRM - Strategic Raw Material

CRMA - Critical Raw Materials Act

End of Life

LCA - Life Cycle Assessment

ISO - International Organization for Standardization

GWP - Global Warming Potential

AFPMSM - Axial Flux Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor

FEM - Finite Element Methods

CFD - Computational Fluid Dynamics

SOC - State of Charge

PI - Proportional-Integral

REX - Range Extender

ICE - Internal Combustion Engine

PHEV - Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicle

WLTC - Worldwide Harmonized Light Vehicles Test Cycle

UNECE - United Nations Economic Commission for Europe

NEDC - New European Driving Cycle

PMR - Power-to-Mass Ratio

FTP - Federal Test Procedure

EPA - U.S. Environmental Protection Agency

KDE - Kernel Density Estimation

LCIA - Life Cycle Impact Assessment

ADP - Abiotic Depletion Potential

AE - Accumulated Exceedance

BEP - Break Even Point

FC - Fuel Consumption

FRV - Fuel Reduction Value